

Systematic Technical Report for Model-driven Elicitation of Functional and Security Requirements in AI-supported Systems

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Abstract. This report encompasses the systematic literature review conducted for the development of an artefact (An AI-supported system model). In this document, we provide an in-depth analysis of concepts derived from the SLR and processes of its derivation, shown as figures and tables across this document. The document presents the feasibility study conducted using Z-Inspection and the results obtained from the study.

1 Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems are rapidly transforming the way businesses operate. This evolution has led to the business adoption of the technology, which is inherently associated with security risks through vulnerabilities and impacts the system. Security risks targeting AI systems have demonstrated that traditional software security measures are insufficient in addressing these risks, which stem from the architectural and operational characteristics of the AI system.

Current approaches to AI security risk management face several fundamental limitations. While there are existing valuable frameworks - such as MITRE ATLAS [1], OWASP AI Exchange [2] that bring the taxonomic approach to addressing AI security, they offer limited guidance on how to systematically apply these concepts to specific AI system architectures during the design phase. Similarly, traditional risk management lacks the granular constructs necessary to model AI-specific assets and their lifecycle. This gap necessitates measuring the truthworthiness of an AI system (with respect to security) through the implementation of requirements engineering in design, rather than as an afterthought, leaving businesses vulnerable to AI-specific attacks.

This technical report addresses this gap by presenting a model-driven method for engineering trustworthy AI-supported systems. Our work presents two contributions: first, we detail the development of a novel AI-supported model (see Figure 3) developed through a systematic literature review (SLR) and grounded in the Design Science Research Principles using the Information Systems Security Risk Management (ISSRM) domain model as a guiding baseline. To develop the model, the Unified Modelling Language (UML) and the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) have been chosen to describe assets and processes within the AI lifecycle, thereby facilitating the adaptation of AI into organisational systems.; second, we present the results of the feasibility study applying the proposed model and derived functional and security requirements within the Z-inspection process to evaluate the coverage of trustworthiness for an AI system. By providing both theoretical and empirical validation, this report demonstrates how businesses can systematically elicit functional and security requirements, identify architectural

gaps, and verify the overall trustworthiness of their AI systems, thereby driving discussions among multidisciplinary teams on AI development and security.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the background and related work. Section 3 presents the methodology for model development, including SLR processes and a conceptual modelling approach. Section 4 presents the artefacts developed (core conceptual model and its components). Section 4 describes the feasibility study and implementation of the z-inspection. Section 5 concludes the technical report with future directions.

2 Background

Security Risk Management: Security risk management involves identifying, assessing, and mitigating security risks by monitoring and controlling the likelihood of threats that exploit a system’s vulnerabilities. The Information Systems Security Risk Management (ISSRM) [3] is a systematic approach to determining and managing security risks within an organisation’s system. The ISSRM domain model consists of three (3) key concepts: asset-related concepts, risk-related concepts, and risk treatment-related concepts (see Figure 1). Asset-related concepts define an organisation’s assets that are important to protect. Risk-related concepts describe how risks can be mitigated and treated. The risk treatment involves addressing associated risks by refining security requirements and implementing various control measures to mitigate risk.

Figure 1: The ISSRM Domain Model adapted from [3]

Frameworks: The NIST AI RMF [4] provides an understanding of the risks, impact and harms of an AI system. The framework addresses risks as they emerge, given that the AI ecosystem is vast and constantly evolving; therefore, directives on assessing the adverse effects of AI systems are ongoing. The core AI RMF provides different activities to manage AI risks, including mapping the context and risks, measuring the identified risk through analysis, and prioritising the risk based on its projected impact. MITRE ATLAS (Adversarial Threat Landscape for Artificial Intelligence Systems) [1] maps real-world threats of AI systems as a knowledge base. The framework documents tactics, techniques, and case studies of adversarial attacks against machine learning models. The matrix provides an understanding of the vulnerabilities and provides mitigation strategies for the AI threat landscape. The OWASP LLM TOP 10 classifies

and addresses security threats specific to Large Language Model (LLM) applications, ranging from prompt injection to unbound consumption [5]. ENISA[6] provides a path for defenders of the AI system to approach these attacks from the perspective of the life cycle, thereby increasing the need to access AI systems within the various scopes of the lifecycle. In the context of the trustworthiness of AI systems, the European Union’s AI Act regulation [7], developed by the European Commission, formally establishes a regulatory framework on a risk-based approach, mandating that AI systems must meet strict requirements for robustness, accuracy, and security.

Z-Inspection: The Z-Inspection [8] is a process designed to assess the trustworthiness of AI systems. The process employs an analytical approach to consider various components of the AI system. The approach supports a multidisciplinary group of experts in assessing the ethical, technical, and legal implications of AI. The process is performed interactively in three phases: setup, assessment, and resolution. In this paper, we employ the Z-inspection to conduct a feasibility study on assessing the trustworthiness of AI in terms of its security.

3 Systematic Literature Review

A systematic literature review (SLR) following the guidelines [9] as a baseline for the development of the conceptual model. To develop the proposed model, the following questions were designed to answer our main research question is **”MRQ1: How can security risks in AI systems be managed?”** through the following sub-questions:

- **RQ1:** What is the Context of the AI/ML system?
- **RQ2:** What are AI/ML Security Risks?
- **RQ3:** What are security countermeasures to mitigate AI/ML security risk?

3.1 Sources Selection

The search for relevant literature was conducted across the following digital libraries: Scopus, IEEE, ACM Digital Library, and Web of Science. In addition, some grey literature sources are included for analysis, which were received outside of repositories dedicated to academic papers, through an unsystematic general search. The MITRE ATLAS framework was a primary source of grey knowledge. It was included in the research because it contributes to the paper’s goal of developing a framework for understanding.

3.2 Search Terms

We applied various keyword combinations to identify relevant literature for developing the conceptual model. Keywords were targeted to cover the scope of interest of the research as follows:

- AI/ML Security
- System components of AI systems
- Threat modelling of the AI system
- AI lifecycle

For the IEEE, the following queries were utilised to understand the concepts of security for AI: (“threat model of artificial intelligence” OR “threat model of AI” OR “threat model of machine learning” OR “threat model of ML” OR “threat model of large language model” OR “threat

model of LLM”) OR (“security of large language models” OR “security of LLM” OR “Artificial Intelligence System” AND “security of AI” OR “security of machine learning” OR “security of ML”)

For Scopus, ACM Digital Library and Web of Science, we used the following combinations to further refine the keywords:

1. (“security of large language models” OR “security of LLM” OR “security of artificial intelligence” OR “security of AI” OR “security of machine learning” OR “security of ML”)
2. (“Artificial Intelligence system” AND “Security”)
3. (“AI Lifecycle” OR “ML lifecycle” AND “AI Security”)

These Keyword combinations provide a basis for the expected results of the literature to further our analysis.

3.3 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The following Inclusion criteria were considered for this research:

- Research related to security, attacks, and threat modelling of artificial intelligence
- Papers whose primary language is English
- Paper in the scope of artificial intelligence, machine learning, data security and cybersecurity
- scientific conference and peer-reviewed journals
- Papers within the years of 2019-2025. These years were chosen because of the rapid changes happening within the Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning field; thus, we could adapt to recent changes in our work.

The following exclusion criteria were considered for this research:

- Papers out of year range
- Not written in English
- Not freely accessible
- other subject areas not related to our keywords, such as papers addressing other areas of AI and ML subsets

3.4 Paper Selection

The selection of relevant research papers from academic digital repositories was conducted by defined keyword combinations in Chapter 3.1.1 throughout the October 2024 - April period in 2025.

The quantitative result of the search is provided in Figure 2. The total number of papers under review is 63. The selection was conducted with the following steps:

1. Conduct a request based on the described combination of keywords;
2. The screening of the papers undergoes three stages

- Manually inspect the provided set of research papers based on their title and abstract, following the defined inclusion and exclusion criteria, as defined in section 3.3
- The collected set of papers was additionally checked for duplicates across digital repositories;
- More in-depth reading of each paper at this stage was conducted to assess the quality of the paper.

Figure 2: **Flowchart for conducting the SLR .**

3.5 Quality Assessment

To assess the quality of the 500 remaining papers, we established four quality assessment criteria that extend the inclusion criteria outlined in Section 3.3. The Quality assessment was carried out through an in-depth reading of full-text articles, using the CASP checklist [10], using a 'YES, MAYBE and NO' response to questions. The questions reviewed are as follows.

1. Did the paper clearly address aspects of AI security that focused on our research question?
2. Does the paper have a defined research approach to how the results were achieved?
3. Did the paper fully or partially provide security control measures for AI systems?
4. Are the conclusions drawn in the paper providing a context for how AI systems can be managed?

After this process, 470 papers were excluded from further synthesis as they did not fully or partially meet our selection criteria. The remaining 30 papers were selected for further data synthesis and extraction.

3.6 Data Extraction

The data extraction form is designed to collect the relevant information needed to address our research problem and answer the review questions. The following information was extracted in a Table 1: **Paper Title, Authors, Year of publication, AI Lifecycle, System Asset, Business Asset, Threat Agent, Attack Name, Security Requirements, Security Control.**

Table 1: Information extraction for data synthesis of results retrieved from the systematic literature review

Information Extracted	Interpretation
Paper Title	The title of the paper
Author	The author or authors of the paper
Year of Publication	The publication year of the paper
Business Assets	various types of data on which an AI system operates
System Assets	hardware, software processes, and components of the AI system
AI Lifecycle	The processes of the lifecycle with the AI system
Threat Name	The type of threat targeted to asset of the AI system
Threat agent	an adversary and their capabilities
Security Requirements	a security requirement for the system to meet, to become resistant to the related attack
Security control	tools, methods for mitigating security risks in AI systems

3.7 Results

In this section, we present the results of data extracted from the literature. We tabulate the data extracted to answer each of the review questions based on the primary study.

3.7.1 AI/ML system context

This section addresses RQ1: What is the context of the AI/ML System? presenting the core components of the system. The context is defined through the business and system assets of an AI system. The business asset (Table 2) represents high-value information that supports the system’s functioning. These assets are information which should follow the security criteria of confidentiality, integrity and availability. The system asset (Table3) are the various components that make up the AI system. Furthermore, this section presents the AI lifecycle (see Table 4) as the dynamic context in which assets operate. The defined processes within each lifecycle describe how the system interacts, thereby operationalising the business assets.

3.7.2 Description of Business assets

Training data: data sets utilised to train, retrain, or fine-tune the target machine learning model [19]. In the context of LLMs, this could be a large collection of textual data. This asset is utilised during the training process to train the model. [12]. The data may be taken from the prepared public data sets, collected through web resources with web crawlers, or from internal services [26]

Test Data: These test data are withheld during the training and used in the final evaluation of the model. They provide an unbiased assessment of the model’s operation because the model does not learn from this dataset.

Model Data Operation: are transient and intermediate data and calculations generated and executed during the Model’s operational inference stage.

Model parameters: integral components of a model critical to its operation and utility We consider the following component parameters: layers, type of activation function, layer connections, parameters, and weights. If the machine learning model is removed, the parameters are also removed because they are interdependent.

Input Data: The input data, which originates from applications that utilise external APIs [16], user input, and databases, is the new data used for the predictions or functionality of the trained model.

Table 2: Extracted business assets reported in reviewed studies

Business Asset							
Paper Ref	Training data	Test data	Input Data Embeddings	Model Data Operation	Model Parameters	Input Data	Intellectual Property
[11]	Datasets, Training Data	Test data	-	-	-	-	
[12]	Datasets	-	-	-	Hyper-parameter	-	-
[13]	Synthetic data	Validation data, Training samples	-	-	-	-	-
[14]	Real data, Training data	-	-	-	-	-	-
[15]	Training data	Test data, Training samples	-	-	Model Parameters	-	-
[16]	Training data	Test data	-	-	-	-	-
[17]	Training data	-	-	-	-	-	-
[18]	Training data	Test data	-	-	-	-	-
[19]	Training data	Test data	-	-	Model Parameters	-	-
[20]	Training data	Test data	-	-	-	-	-
[21]	-	Test data	-	-	-	-	-
[?]	-	Training sample	-	-	-	-	-
[22]	-	ML Embeddings	-	-	-	-	-
[23]	-	-	Input Features	-	-	-	-
[24]	-	-	-	Operational Data	-	-	-
[25]	-	-	-	-	-	Input Data	-
[26]	Training data	Test data	Input Data Embeddings	Model Data operation	Model parameters	Input Data	Intellectual Property

Intellectual property: consists of legal rights and protections, proprietary methods and designs associated with the produced machine learning model and its components. Intellectual property underlines a company’s competitive advantage and can incorporate developed trade secrets and patents.

3.7.3 Description of system assets and their relationships

1. **Machine Learning (ML) Model:** The ”Machine Learning Model” is defined as the core asset that is supported by other system assets to enable its performance [26]. Also, the ML model acts as both a system (a software component with relation to other assets) and a business asset (driving the business logic and informed decisions). For example, as an artefact produced from a training process [13].

The ML model runs algorithms such as conventional linear regressions, decision trees, support vector machines (SVM), or neural networks [19]. The algorithm (*Preprocessed model*) is trained on data (*Trained ML model*) to refine it (*Refined ML model*) by learning patterns, which improves predictions, enables complex computations, and informs decisions (*Deployed model*). These different assets are accessed through the state transitions of the ML model, which are represented as an enumeration in relation to the model’s development. The ML model class (system asset) is associated with the model parameters [15, 19, 12] and intellectual property. The model parameters are integral components of a model [19], internal variables critical to its operation and utility. The values of the parameters are adjusted during the training process. consists of legal rights and protec-

tions, proprietary methods, and design associated with the machine learning model and its components.

2. **Machine Learning Training System** defines the system for training and testing ML models. This is a "combination of processes and procedures, hardware and software infrastructure dedicated to the training, fine-tuning and creation of the ML model, thus updating the model parameters in the process" [26]. The ML Training System class encompasses the Data generation, Training and Testing stages of the AI lifecycle (see Figure ?? for lifecycle stages).

The ML training system trains the Model using sets of *training data*, a business asset associated with the ML model. These are the datasets to train, test and refine the ML model [16]. The methods (*pre-processTrainingData()*, *trainModel()*, *testandRefineMLModel()*, and *continueModelTuning ()*) represent functions and operations of the system assets performed by the Machine Learning Training System. There may be multiple (*) training systems dedicated to one ML model.

3. **ML Processing system:** The system consists of "enabling system components", "supporting IT infrastructure", and "preprocessing system". It is a high-level representation of the collection of these systems and the operations of the deployed ML model. The "Model operational data" are intermediate and transient data and calculations generated and executed during the Model's operational deployment stage.
4. **Enabling software components:** The machine learning model uses, relies on, and consists of software frameworks, hardware components [20], libraries, and runtime environments necessary for its development, training, and operation. The deployment system includes graphic processing units (GPUs) [16, 27] or the resources that provide computing at the edge [12]. (*storeMLEmbeddingsandOperations()*, *createMLModel()*, *deployMLModel()*, and *processingQueryInputData()*) represent functions performed by the Enabling software components class, and there can be multiple (*) components which enable their operations to one ML model.
5. **Supporting IT infrastructure:** constitutes the broader computational environment (servers, networking, database services, and cloud services) required to deploy, run, and maintain the ML model. This infrastructure enables the auxiliary operations [16, 26] such as the storage and provisioning of business asset like "Input data embeddings" [13, 16, 28]. (representations of data created during training or inference).
6. **ML System input API** is a combination of software and hardware systems, acting as an external interface to the target model. External users or client applications use the interface to submit input data, perform inference operations on it, and receive the results of the operation in response. The *input data*, which comes from applications that use external APIs [16], user inputs, and databases, is the new data provided for the predictions or functionality of the trained Model.

3.7.4 Description of the AI Lifecycle

Data Processing stage [21, 12]: At this stage, data is captured for training and alignment of a model with a particular task. Data preprocessing is performed to transform the gathered data into a suitable format and to ensure the statistical quality of the created dataset [26].

Table 3: Extracted system assets reported in reviewed studies

Paper Ref	System Asset					
	Machine Learning Training System	ML System Input API	Machine Learning Model	ML Processing System	Supporting IT Infrastructure	Enabling Software Components*
[29]	Training System	-	Machine learning model	-	-	-
[11]	Training System	-	-	-	-	-
[19]	-	API	-	-	-	-
[30]	-	-	-	Processing hardware running the ML model*	-	-
[15]	-	-	-	-	Software Operating System	Libraries
[16]	-	API	-	-	-	-
[24]	-	-	ML model components	Processing hardware running the ML model	-	-
[20]	-	Deployment Environment	-	-	-	-
[31]	-	-	Machine learning model	-	-	-
[27]	-	-	-	-	Supporting IT Infrastructure	Enabling software components
[26]	Machine Learning System	ML System Input API	Machine Learning Model	ML Processing System	Supporting IT Infrastructure	Enabling Software Components

Training stage: During the training stage, the model's parameters are iteratively adjusted to minimise the error rate, while keeping the model generalised. Model parameters are updated iteratively based on the properties of the training dataset. Example training techniques: back propagation and gradient descent [16, 26, 12]. At this stage, the ML model undergoes the development phase [20], and an appropriate preprocessed model is chosen to carry out the task. The training is guided by optimising a loss function, which quantifies the model's prediction errors.

Testing stage: During the training phase, the performance of the produced model is assessed with test data. The assessment guides the following training iterations to achieve an optimal model performance.

Deployment stage: When the optimal model is produced, it is integrated into the production application, service, or system, while selecting an appropriate platform and infrastructure for it.

Application stage: An operation state, when the deployed trained model is utilised to make a decision based on the submitted new, unseen input data. The input data are processed using the learnt logic, resulting in the generation of output data.

3.7.5 Security Risks of AI systems

This section provides an answer to Research Question 2: What are the security risks associated with AI systems? The elicited threats present the threats that harm the AI system, as extracted. The table shows the defined terms (Data, Model Application threats) which we used to categorise the different threats found in the literature.

3.7.6 Description of concepts for AI Threats

Data Threats: At this level, the attacker targets the vulnerabilities of the AI/ML system **Enabling Software Component** running the ML model and the **Machine Learning Training System**. Threats at the data level negate the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of business assets. Hence, it is crucial to understand the threats at each distinct level. (see Table 5)

Table 4: Extracted AI lifecycle stages identified across the reviewed studies

AI Lifecycle					
Paper Ref	Data Processing Stage	Training Stage	Testing Stage	Deployment Stage	Application Stage
[21]	-	Model development	Testing	Deployment	Connection to business app
[13]	Data Generation	Model Training	-	Model deployment, Inference phase	-
[15]	-	Training phase	Testing time	-	-
[16]	-	Training	-	Deployment	-
[17]	-	Training	Testing	-	-
[32]	-	-	Testing	-	-
[14]	-	Training phase	-	Inference phase	Application phase
[26]	-	-	-	Embedding vectors	-
[19]	-	Training phase	Testing phase	-	-
[20]	-	Training, Model development	Testing	-	-
[23]	-	Training	Testing	Model deployment	Inference
[33]	-	Training, Development	Testing	Data storage	-
[28]	-	Training	-	-	-
[27]	-	-	Testing	-	-
[12]	Raw data processing	Model Training, Feature extraction	Testing	-	-

1. **Data poisoning attacks (AML.T0020)** is a technique that occurs during the data generation, training and testing stages. The attacker attempts to poison training data by modifying or tampering with its underlying data or ML artefacts (such as labels, parameters and intellectual property). The attacker can define the classification function of the model, thus supporting its operations during training. **Tactic:** Resource Development and Persistence - AML.TA0003, AML.TA0006
2. **Backdoor attacks(AML.T0043.004)** provides an instance where the attacker poisons or manipulates the labels to misbehave when a backdoor key is present but performs well with training data [16, 34]. **Tactic:** ML Attack Staging - AML.TA0001
3. **Supply Chain Attack (AML.T0010.002)** is a type of attack resulting from data compromise by capture and transmission in the data generation phase. Machine learning relies on a large amount of data (open source data or libraries), so an attacker uses the leverage of the supply chain to compromise the data source [15]. **Tactic:** Initial Access and ML supply chain compromise-AML.TA0004, AML.T0010.002

Model Threats: The ML model is another core part of the AI/ML system. At this level, attackers introduce threats that compromise the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the model, causing it to misrepresent, misinterpret, or produce incorrect results. (see Table 6) The model level encompasses the threat occurrences that occur within the training, testing, and deployment phases of the AI/ML system lifecycle.

1. **Model poisoning (AML.T0018.00)** alters the trained ML model by introducing malicious features [19]. During training, for example, the attacker can misclassify or misrepresent the model, thereby distorting the system's classification function [34]. The model poisoning attack also introduces backdoor injection, affecting the training process. **Tactic:** ML Attack Staging AML.TA0001, Persistence AML.TA0006
2. **Model Evasion (AML.T0015)** threatens the integrity of the ML model. In this case, the attacker crafts a misclassified or added noise to mislead the model, whether through white-box or black-box access. This attack tricks the ML model into making incorrect predictions, acting on the attacker's plot, and can be likened to the algorithm exploitation attack [28]. **Tactic:** Defense Evasion (AML.TA0007)

Table 5: Extracted Data-related threats identified across the reviewed studies.

Paper Ref	Data Threats					
	Data Poisoning	Supply Chain attack	Membership Inference	Back-door attack	Data Breach	Data Extraction
[21]	+	-	-	-	-	-
[13]	+	-	-	-	-	-
[15]	+	-	+	-	-	-
[16]	+	-	-	+	-	-
[17]	+	-	-	-	-	-
[29]	+	-	-	+	-	-
[32]	-	-	-	-	+	-
[14]	+	-	-	-	-	-
[35]	+	-	-	+	-	-
[26]	-	-	+	-	-	-
[19]	+	-	-	-	-	-
[20]	-	-	-	-	-	-
[11]	+	-	-	-	-	-
[23]	-	-	-	-	-	-
[36]	-	-	-	-	-	-
[33]	+	-	-	+	-	-
[28]	-	-	-	-	-	-
[27]	-	-	-	-	-	+
[12]	+	-	-	-	-	-
MITRE ATLAS	AML.T0020	AML.T0010.002	AML.T0043.004	-	-	-

3. **Model Denial of Service (AML.T0029)** targets the **Enabling System Component** and the **ML system Input API** system with a flood of requests to degrade the model or query performance. This Enabling System Component is overwhelmed by a target-trained model, which shuts down or slows the system’s computational capability [15, 16]. During input data processing, attackers can potentially craft inputs that result in the degradation of the Enabling System Component. **Tactic:** Impact AML.TA0011
4. **Model Extraction (AML.T0024.002)** targets the **Enabling System Component**, giving aid to stealing and extracting the ML model’s inference or the private model such as the *model parameters and intellectual property* to replicate or duplicate the model (the attacker in this case, trains an offline model that performs the same function as the stolen model). **Tactic:** Exfiltration (AML.TA0010)
5. **Model Inversion (AML.T0024.001):** This attack targets the **Machine Learning Training System** to reverse engineer its *input data* in the target model. This attack can also be viewed as data reconstruction, where the *training data* is reconstructed solely for the purpose of generating the output data. Over-fitted ML models are prone to this attack because they can leak sensitive information on which they were trained, giving the attacker leverage over the information and affecting both the confidentiality and integrity of the *training data* and *ML model*.

Application Threats: This level addresses threats targeted to the **ML System Input API**. This threat impacts *trained ML models* and *input data*, compromising their integrity and availability, thereby hindering reliable model performance in producing the correct *query result*. (see Table 7)

1. **Prompt Injection (AML.T0051):** Prompt injection attacks occur mainly with large language models (LLMs). The attacker crafts malicious prompts as input data to the **ML System Input API**, causing the trained ML model to behave abnormally by producing harmful *query results*. Prompt injections can be direct or indirect depending on the context in which the input data was crafted [15, 20]. Attackers can exploit the vulnerabilities of the trained ML model to leak sensitive data (*intellectual property*), altering the initial training of the model. **Tactic:** Execution, Exfiltration (AML.TA0005,AML.TA0010)

Table 6: Extracted model-related threats identified across the reviewed studies.

Paper Ref	Model Threats						
	Model Poisoning	Model Evasion	Model Inversion	Model Extraction	Algorithm Exploitation	Ex-	Model Denial of Service
[21]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[13]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
[15]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[16]	+	-	+	-	-	-	+
[17]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[29]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[32]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
[14]	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
[35]	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
[26]	+	-	-	+	-	-	-
[19]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[20]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[11]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[23]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[36]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[33]	+	-	-	-	-	-	-
[28]	+	-	-	-	+	-	-
[27]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[12]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
MITRE ATLAS	AML.T0018.00	AML.T0015	AML.T0024.001	AML.T0024.02	AML.T0035		AML.T0029

2. **Unauthorised Model Modification (AML.T0043.003)**: The attacker may exploit the vulnerabilities of the ML model by using the *input data* to inject adversarial data or malicious code into the ML model operation, hence negating its integrity [13]. The model modification is a similar attack to the model poisoning; however, in this case, the attacker tries to modify the model based on the input data [20]. **Tactic**: ML Attack Staging (AML.TA0001)
3. **Model Theft (AML.T0040)**: This is a form of model extraction attack. The attackers pretend to be legitimate users by creating a duplicate model and training it based on the query results retrieved from the real-trained ML model [16]. In another case, the attacker accesses the inference API to gain more information about the training data used in the model, thereby developing a replica of the original model. This form of attack is similar to the model extraction attack. **Tactic**: ML Model Access (AML.TA0000), Impact (AML.T0048.004)

3.7.7 Security Controls

To mitigate threats, various control measures have been proposed in the literature to enhance the reliability of AI systems. In Table 8 and 9, we present them based on threats and the corresponding control measures.

Data Validation (AML.M008): acts as a defence mechanism during data pre-processing. The history of the data set is maintained to ensure that the training data is correct and useful before it is used for ML Model training.

Data sanitisation (AML.M0007): is a measure in which the training dataset is filtered or removed to limit misleading data [19]. This control refines the process, thus identifying maliciously crafted data samples that misled the model's performance and resilience to a data poisoning attack. Data poisoning mitigation is critical in the development of AI/ML systems because they create a pathway for other forms of the attack, such as a **backdoor** or **supply chain** attack; thus, techniques such as inspecting and validating the data [15, 27], and testing to understand the capabilities of the attacker are essential measures. **Model Perturbation Technique**

Table 7: Extracted application-related threats identified across the reviewed studies

Paper Ref	Application Threats				
	Prompt Injection	Injection	Unauthorised Model Modification	Model Theft	Manipulation of Input Data
[21]	-		-	-	-
[13]	-		+	-	-
[15]	+		-	-	-
[16]	-		-	+	-
[17]	-		-	-	-
[29]	-		-	-	-
[32]	-		-	-	-
[14]	-		-	-	-
[35]	-		-	-	-
[26]	+		+	-	+
[19]	-		-	-	+
[20]	+		-	-	-
[11]	-		-	-	-
[23]	-		-	-	-
[36]	-		-	-	+
[33]	-		-	-	-
[28]	-		-	-	+
[27]	-		-	-	-
[12]	-		-	-	-
MITRE ATLAS	AML.T0051		AML.T0043.003	AML.T0040	AML.T0018

(AML.M0002): This measure consists of adjusting and obscuring sensitive information of the model parameters (weights) [15].

Artefact Verification (AML.M0014): This method validates that AI models perform as intended by testing for backdoor triggers or adversarial influence. Monitor model for concept drift and training data drift, which may indicate data tampering and poisoning.

Differential Privacy: This measure includes the addition of noise to data by ensuring the model does not reveal sensitive information about individual data points.

Regularisation: This form of control prevents the model from overfitting. This means that the ML model learns from the training data, covering noise and random fluctuations. Hence, for model poisoning and model modifications, attackers could add noise to the model itself, causing overfitting and misleading the predictions made by the ML model. **Cross-validation:** mitigates model poisoning or modifications to the model by implementing evaluations by averaging the performance of the ML model. It is a statistical technique for the generalisability of the ML model, thus providing multiple estimates of the model performance [15].

Model Ensemble Learning (AML.M0006): This method increases the robustness of the model by introducing an ensemble of models. Attacks on a model by an attacker do not effectively affect other models within the system.

Adversarial training: AML.M0003: This method involves the injection of adversarial examples into the training such that the model learns how to be secured from malicious inputs of perturbations.

Access Control (AML.M005): Techniques such as access control [15] are applied to limit training data to approved personnel in charge of the machine learning training system.

Anomaly Detection (AML.M0015): This measure provides the identification of patterns, such as frequent input from the user overwhelming the ML model, which deviates from the considered process of the ML model. This form of mitigation provides monitoring to defend ML models.

Model Monitoring: This process involves monitoring, tracking and evaluation of the ML model and its behaviour within inference. It ensures that the model is accurate and the model parameters are secured.

Contextual Analysis: This method is provided to the model based on contexts to detect

Table 8: Security Controls (Part 1)

Security Controls						
Paper Ref	Data validation	Data Sanitization	Model Perturbation Technique	Artefact Verification	Differential Privacy	Regularization/Cross-validation
[21]	Data Poisoning	-	-	-	-	-
[13]	-	-	-	Supply Chain attack	-	Model Poisoning
[15]	-	-	Model Inversion	-	Model Inversion	Unauthorized Model Modification
[16]	-	-	-	-	Membership Inference	-
[32]	-	Backdoor attack	-	-	-	-
[14]	-	-	-	-	-	-
[35])	-	-	-	-	-	-
[26]	-	-	Model Extraction	-	Membership Inference	Membership Inference
[19]	-	-	-	-	-	-
[20]	-	Data Poisoning	-	-	-	-
[11]	-	-	-	Supply Chain attack	-	-
[27]	-	-	-	-	Membership Inference	-
MITRE ATLAS	AML.M008	AML.M0007	AML.M0002	AML.M0014	-	-

whether an input from a user is trying to inject malicious data into the model instructions [11]. It is an automated check and guardrail for ML models before the text is processed by the model.

Encryption (AML.M0012): This is a form of control which encrypts sensitive data, such as AI models, to protect against attackers attempting to access sensitive data.

Model Pruning: This control is a measure on identifying less significant parts of the model parameters (weight) by removing individual weights and reducing the size of unused model parameters. This control minimises the risk of an attacker poisoning the ML model parameters or manipulating the input data to affect the model's weights [14].

4 Results of Artefact Development

4.1 Conceptual Asset-Lifecycle Centric Framework

The conceptual model is developed using the Unified Modelling Language (UML). This model (see. Figure 3) shows the relationship between the assets and their operations. Provides a static model for an AI asset lifecycle-centric method to manage security risks. Businesses must first discover what makes up the system (assets) that security threats can target and at what stage of the lifecycle such threats are liable to exist.

This section answers the main research question of this research. MRQ: How can AI/ML systems be managed? Based on the results of the SLR (see 3.7), we sought to answer the MRQ by providing the context of the AI system as the business, system and AI Lifecycle. The system assets are classified into six concepts (*Machine Learning (ML) Model, Machine Learning Training System, ML Processing System, Enabling Software Components, Supporting IT Infrastructure, and ML System Input API*) as components and tools that support the AI system. The business assets, which are the core information that drives the business or solution, are (*Training data, Test data, pre-processed ML model, Refined ML Model, Trained/Deployed ML model, Input data embeddings, Model Data Operations, Model Parameters, Query Input Data, Query Result and Intellectual Property*). We also defined the AI lifecycle process within each of the system assets. The Asset-lifecycle centric model also presents the different states of the ML model, showing the behaviour of the model as it passes through each life cycle. The result of these states is also described as a business asset which could face security attacks at any time.

Figure 3: **Synthesis of Result.** Conceptual Asset-Lifecycle Centric Framework for AI/ML systems

Table 9: Security Controls (Part 2)

Security Controls							
Paper Ref	Model Ensemble Learning	Adversarial Training	Access Control	Anomaly Detection	Model Monitoring	Contextual Analysis	Encryption/Model Pruning
[21]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[13]	Model Poisoning	Model Evasion	-	Unauthorized Model Modification	-	-	-
[15]	-	-	Supply Chain attack	Model Denial of Service	Model Extraction	Prompt Injection	-
[16]	-	-	Model Extraction	Model Denial of Service	-	-	Model Theft
[32]	-	-	-	-	-	-	Manipulation of Input data
[14]	-	-	-	-	Model Extraction	-	-
[35]	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
[26]	-	-	Data Poisoning	-	-	-	-
[19]	-	-	-	-	-	-	Model Poisoning
[20]	-	Model Evasion	Data Poisoning	-	-	-	-
[11]	-	-	-	-	-	Prompt Injection	-
[27]	-	-	-	-	Data Extraction	-	-
MITRE ATLAS	AML.M0006	AML.M0003	AML.M0005	AML.M0015	-	-	AML.M0012

4.2 Process diagram of training and deploying AI

Training Process: Figure 4 shows the **Machine Learning Training System** that preprocesses data, trains and tests the model to evaluate the performance of the model before its deployment for use. The **Enabling Software Component** stores the ML embeddings and operational data (*Model Data Operation and Input Data Embeddings*) used in creating the ML Model, consisting of the Preprocessed ML model (*Model parameters and Intellectual property*). The Preprocessed ML model is trained on the training data based on a defined set of parameters in the training activity, resulting in a *Trained ML model*. The *Trained ML model* undergoes testing and refinement using the *test data* to evaluate the model's performance (*Refined ML model*). In the deployment stage, the *Refined ML model* is converted to a deployable format (for example, Tensorflow, Pickle, Safetensors) and wrapped into an API. For example, cloud environments serve as the enabling software components that host ML models deployed using GPUs for high-performance inference [16].

Process Query and Continuous Tuning: Figure 5 presents the processes within the application stage, the **ML System Input API** processes the input data provided by the user (*Received Input Data*), and the output of the processed input data (*Query Input Data*) is sent to the **Enabling Software Component**. In this activity, the processing of the *Query Input Data* results in the final *Query Result* sent to the **ML System Input API**. For continuous tuning of the model (*Refined ML model*), the *Query Input data* is sent to the **Machine Learning Training System** to tune the model based on the new input data received from the **ML System Input API**.

4.3 Functional Requirements for AI-supported System

This section presents the functional requirements derived from the proposed model and defines the operations of a secure AI-supported system. These requirements outline the system's functionality, focusing on the core architectural components: Machine Learning Training System, ML Processing System (Enabling system component), Machine Learning Model, and ML System Input API. The elicited requirements are structured to align with the process operations within each system asset. Table 10 presents the functional requirements for each architectural component.

Figure 4: Training Process of ML Model

Machine Learning Training System (REQ1) describes tools, services, activities, and processes responsible for the training of a machine learning model. The functional requirements require that it should handle data processing (REQ1.1), provide the execution of training the ML model (REQ1.2), validate the model performance through testing and refinement (REQ1.3) and provide a mechanism for continuous model tuning (REQ1.4).

The ML Processing System (REQ2) comprises the Preprocessing system, Enabling software components, and supporting IT infrastructure. Its functions include the storage of model artefacts such as ML Embeddings and Operational Data (REQ2.1), the function needed for creation of the model (REQ2.2), the deployment of the model to production environment (REQ2.3) and processing of input queries to perform inference using deployed data (REQ2.4)

Machine Learning Model is a core component of the AI system. It is the combination of processes and procedures, as well as hardware and software infrastructure, dedicated to training, fine-tuning, and creating the ML model. The requirement REQ3.1 provides the system with the function of tracking the model's progress through these states.

The ML System input API (REQ4) is a combination of software and hardware systems that act as an external interface to the target model. As the primary interface for system interactions, the system should process the input data (REQ4.1) and have the flexibility of managing the formats of data as received or query input data (REQ4.2). These elicited functional requirements provide the specification for developing an AI system by the different stakeholders (such as the system architects). In the following section, we will build upon the functional requirements to derive security requirements to protect the components and operations of the AI-powered system.

Table 10: Architecture and Process Requirements for AI-supported Systems

ReqID	Architectural Component	Functional Requirements
REQ1	Machine Learning Training system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REQ1.1: The Machine Learning Training System should pre-process training data. • REQ1.2: The Machine Learning Training System should train the Model. • REQ1.3: The Machine Learning Training System should test and refine the ML model. • REQ1.4: The Machine Learning Training system should continuously tune the model
REQ2	ML Processing System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REQ2.1: The Enabling software components should store ML Embeddings and Operational Data • REQ2.2: The Enabling software components should create an ML Model • REQ2.3: The Enabling software components should deploy the ML model • REQ2.4: The Enabling software components should process the query input data
REQ3	Machine Learning Model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REQ3.1: The Machine Learning Model should be able to transform into a different state (Preprocessed, Trained, Refined and Deployed)
REQ4	ML system input API	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REQ4.1: The ML system input API should process the input data • REQ4.2: The ML system input API should process the input data as received and query the input data

Figure 5: Query-response process depicting the Assets of the AI System

4.4 Threat Modelling for AI systems

Figure 6 presents the conceptualised model represented as a threat-modelling model which classifies security threats based on defined requirements: *Data threats* (targets the machine learning training system and splits into data preprocessing, train/test model), *Model threats* (targets the machine learning model and the components of the enabling system, which encompasses model and deployment) and *Application threats* (targets the API of the ML system in the output API, which encompasses deployment and application). The results of the SLR threats were mapped on the model, identifying the types of threats and to which system the attacker exploits.

4.4.1 Security Requirements

Security requirements are formal specifications of the necessary safeguards designed to mitigate security risks within AI-supported systems. In this work, these requirements have been systematically elicited through the analysis of threats targeted at AI-supported systems and assigned to established security controls. We elicited 14 security requirements for each threat, recognising that for some threats, it may necessitate multiple or the same controls. The use of MITRE ATLAS Technique IDs for threats and Mitigation IDs for controls provides a standard for connecting our findings to an established body of knowledge in AI security. For example, to mitigate data poisoning (AML.T0020), using data validation (AML.M008) as a control measure operationalises the security requirement. This is implemented by enforcing the

Figure 6: The Threat Model

maintenance and monitoring of the training data's integrity before the data pre-processing stage (SRQ1) and monitoring the ML model for concept and training data drift. Table 11 presents the threats, security controls, and security requirements elicited. In Table 7, we present the security requirements using the business process modelling and notation (bpmn) to annotate these requirements into the AI processes.

5 Method of Security Risk Management for AI systems

This section defines the method for security risk management of AI systems (see Figure 8). The process begins with selecting the AI system to be analysed. This AI system is obtained from an external environment, such as companies and the internet, and its documentation is collected. The available AI documentation is used for the instantiation of the AI system using the proposed meta model of the AI-supported system (see Figure 3). The instance of the selected AI system is used for the first evaluation (i.e the AS-IS); therein, the evaluation results retrieved are used to calculate the functionality, security and trustworthiness coverage of the AI system. The next step follows with the security risk analysis of the "AS-IS" instantiated model, which results in an improved instantiated model of the AI system. The second evaluation is conducted on the improved model with the same process, and the coverage of functionality, security and trustworthiness is calculated again. The final output of the method would be the comparison of the As-IS estimates and To-Be estimates. In the following section, we provide a feasibility study of this method.

6 Feasibility analysis of Proposed Model using Z-Inspection

6.1 The setup phase

To conduct the z-inspection, we began the exercise by providing answers to the preconditions, with the reason for conducting the process adapted from Zicari et al. [8]. Table 9 provides the questions, and the following are the answers to the questions provided by the authors of this research:

1. The authors of this research

Table 11: Security Requirements Elicitation

Threats	Security Control	Security Requirement
Data Poisoning (AML.T0020)	Data Validation (AML.M008)	SRQ1: The training data and ML model should be maintained and monitored before data pre-processing
Backdoor attack (AML.T0043.004)	Data Sanitisation (AML.M0007)	SRQ2: Training data should be sanitised before training the ML model
Model Extraction (AML.T0024.002)	Access Control (AML.M005)	SRQ4: Training data and ML model should be limited to only approved users
Model Theft (AML.T0035)	Encryption (AML.M0012)	SR45: The ML model parameters should be protected against an attacker attempting access
Model Denial of Service (AML.T0029)	Anomaly Detection (AML.M0015)	SRQ5: The ML System input API should monitor and limit the number of abnormally large inputs performed in a given amount of time
Unauthorised Model Modification (AML.T0018.001)		SRQ6: The ML model should be monitored for concept and training data drift
Model Poisoning (AML.T0018.00)	Regularisation Model Ensemble Learning (AML.M0006) Model Pruning	SRQ7: The model training process should cross-validate to detect performance inconsistencies of the model SRQ8: Different ML models should be combined to reduce model redundancy SRQ9: The ML model shall maintain integrity by permitting pruning of model parameters that do not degrade the performance of the model
Prompt Injection (AML.T0051)	Contextual Analysis	SRQ10: The ML System input API should perform analysis on user prompts
Model Inversion (AML.T0024.001)	Model Perturbation Technique (AML.M0002)	SRQ11: The ML model parameters should be disrupted to obscure sensitive information
Membership Inference (AML.T0024.000)	Differential Privacy	SRQ12: Noise should be added to training data
Supply Chain attack (AML.T0010)	Artefact verification (AML.M0014)	SRQ13: The AI artefacts should be verified before usage
Model Evasion (AML.T0015)	Adversarial Training (AML.M0003)	SRQ14: The ML model should be hardened to increase robustness of model

2. The inspection is carried out to assess the feasibility of the proposed model-driven requirements and how it is relevant for the derivation of security requirements for AI-supported

Figure 7: Application of security controls to processes using BPMN

Figure 8: Method of Security Risk Management for AI systems

systems.

3. This inspection is relevant for the AI security community, including developers of AI, as well as companies that integrate AI into their processes.
4. We recommend conducting the inspection.
5. The sufficient conditions to be analysed are the functional requirements of the AI-supported system, while the necessary conditions would be the security requirements of protecting the system from harm.
6. The results from the inspection provide a verifiability for developed artefacts in research and development.
7. The results of the inspection would be shared publicly under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike CC BY-NC-SA) license.

6.1.1 Team Formation and Briefing

The team composition was made up of an interdisciplinary team of 3 members, including:

1. Who requested the inspection?
2. Why carry out an inspection?
3. For whom is the inspection relevant?
4. Is it recommended or required (mandatory inspection)?
5. What are the sufficient vs. necessary conditions that need to be analyzed?
6. How are the inspection results to be used? There are different, possible uses of the results of the inspection: e.g. verification, certification, and sanctions (if illegal).
7. Will the results be shared (public) or kept private? In the latter case, the key question is why is it being kept private?

Figure 9: Setup phase initial questions

- An ML Engineer: This team member is a person who understands the technical architectures and development processes of AI systems.
- Two Security Experts: These members possess a deep understanding of the security context of the AI system, as well as knowledge of other existing frameworks for managing security risks.

The team briefing was conducted by the first author of this research, who provided the team with the following documents.

- The proposed Model and process diagrams of processes
- The developed threat model for security risk analysis
- The instantiated model of the Mistral AL Large Language Model architecture
- The instantiated threat model and security control model of Mistral AI Large Language Model architecture
- Applied security requirements depicting the processes for the development of Mistral AI Large Language Model

6.2 Boundaries and context of Mistral AI

This section presents the instantiation of the proposed asset-centric model for existing LLM systems. The chosen model (Mistral Small) is provided under the Apache 2.0 licence with an open codebase that allows for unrestricted use, an official inference library, and documentation on the model's use [37, 26]. The completeness of the proposed model was evaluated using numbers (1, 0.5 and 0), with 1 representing that the system assets map fully to Mistral small. 0.5 signifies that the asset is partially mapped to the model, and 0 represents that there exists no direct mapping with the assets proposed in the model. The completeness formula [26] formula sums the mapping values assigned to a particular asset and divides the sum by the count of the system assets present in the model to determine the completeness of the proposed model.

¹ are as follows;

$$completeness = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n I(Assetspecificmappingscore)_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n I(SystemAsset)_i}$$

¹Formulae is adapted from the co-author's thesis [38]

The mapping is complete, displaying the associations between system assets and business assets with the components of Mistral AI. Table 12 presents the consolidated results of the mapping, the score assigned based on the related components in the Mistral Small model, and the rationale behind the assigned mapped score. Figure 12 presents the threat modelling of the possible security threats targeted at each component of the use case. Figure 3 presents applied controls to the components.

Based on the provided documentation from Mistral [39], all assets that were completely described in the functional requirements were assigned a score of 1. The system asset (Machine Learning Training System) received a score of 0.5 due to the unavailability of documentation for the preprocessing and training pipeline. However, this does not completely rule out the possibility that some LLM models may have a training pipeline within their system.

Table 12: System Assets and Mapping Scores [Adapted from the thesis [26]]

System asset	Mapping score	Rationale
ML System Input/API	1	Identified in "mistral-common" codebase (ChatCompletion-Request) and API codebases. Aligns with the concept of an external interface.
Machine Learning Model	1	The model weights are defined and available in the format of "safetensors" in a Hugging Face repository.
Processing Hardware running the ML Model	1	Can be processed on local desktop hardware or on a cloud platform.
Enabling Software Components	1	The execution of the model requires multiple official libraries (mistral-inference, mistral-common) or a third-party library – vLLM.
Supporting IT Infrastructure	1	Local desktop setup provides the necessary capabilities within the local environment, updated with the required software components. In addition, platforms like Le Plateforme provide the support capabilities for model execution.
ML Processing System	1	A local collection of hardware and software libraries maps to the subsystem assets. Alternatively, the capabilities of a processing system can be provided by a supported cloud platform
ML Learning Training System	0.5	Partial mapping: There is no documentation of the training pipeline. However, there are fine-tuning scripts that fulfil one of the system's functionalities.

6.2.1 Instantiation of Model

The objective of this process is to create a concrete instance of the conceptual model tailored to the use case, as it becomes the central artefact for the feasibility study carried out during this inspection. The authors of the paper have populated the conceptual model with the results obtained from the previous section (see Figure 11). The process is as follows:

- Identify the business assets: This included the Model Parameters, Mistral AI Intellectual Property, Test data, Tokenisers, and Embeddings
- Identify the system assets: Mistral Small, Mistral common/protocol/instruction/request.py, Mistral Fine-tune system, Personal computer with RTX 4090, Mistral common
- Map the operations to the system assets: trainMistralSmall(), MistralFineTune(), continuousModelTuning(), storeEmbeddingandTokeniser(), deployMlmodel(), preprocessingUserQueryInput(), processUserQueryInput()

6.3 The Assess phase

To empirically validate the coverage and effectiveness of the requirements elicited through our model-driven method, a structured expert evaluation was conducted. The process begins with the development of a questionnaire. The questions were derived directly based on the functional and security requirements previously elicited using our conceptual model. The results are captured on a Likert scale (ranging from 1, indicating "Not fulfilled," to 5, indicating "Fully fulfilled")

to help experts determine the extent to which each requirement is covered in the use case. The assessment is analysed across two phases:

- Phase 1: In this initial phase, experts were presented with the baseline instantiated model (see Figure 11), which included the functional architecture. For each system asset and operation, the experts answer questions to determine the degree to which the functional and security requirements of each asset are covered in the instantiated model. (assuming their judgment that proposed security mitigation measures are now in place.)
- Phase 2: In this phase, the same questions are repeated. However, the enhanced version of the instantiated model is presented to experts. This version explicitly incorporates the security requirements (Figure 14) and security controls (see Figure 13). The experts re-evaluate the presented models

This process provides an overview of the coverage and perceived gaps in functional and security requirements, as well as the trustworthiness of the AI system. The following are the defined criteria for assessment:

- Functionality coverage: How well are the defined functional requirements covered in the Mistral AI architecture?
- Security coverage: How well are the security requirements covered within the Mistral AI architecture?
- Trustworthiness coverage: How trustworthy is the Mistral AI with regards to security?

6.4 Results of Z-inspection and feasibility of the study

Figure 10 summarises the findings of the output of the z-inspection process on the perceived trustworthiness of the Instantiated Mistral AI system. The results were captured on a Likert scale (1 = Not fulfilled to 5 = Fully fulfilled) across two phases: the architecture components system, and the same system with security requirements applied. Exp1, Exp2, and Exp3 represent the team of experts who led the Z inspection, and the questions were based on the functional and security requirements defined in the document.

1. Functional Requirements Coverage: The functional requirements (RQ1.1 - RQ4.2) showed positive results for the architectural components, with further improvement after the mitigation.

- Phase 1: The average coverage of the functional requirements was 68.5%. This indicated that the core architecture of the Mistral AI system was well defined and mapped from a functional perspective, even before the security analysis was conducted.
- Phase 2: In this phase, we noticed an improved score of 74.5%. This suggests that the application of security controls helped identify and clarify the ambiguity in the functional requirements, as identified by the experts, leading to a more functional architecture for the Mistral AI system.

The results also showed gaps in the architecture. For example, functional requirements like REQ2.3 and REQ2.4 were consistently scored higher by all experts in both phases, indicating that the component was clearly understood, mapped, and implemented to function as the system asset. The requirement REQ2.2 ("The Enabling software components

should create an ML Model”) remained a low score in both phases (phase 1: 4.0, Phase 2: 6.0). This suggests that the function was not implemented by the system asset (Enabling software components) and provides a potentially significant gap in the system’s model creation functionality. Notably, requirement 4.2 decreased in phase 2, with a coverage of 7.0 against 10.0 in phase 1. This could indicate the expert’s subjective perception.

2. **Security Requirement Coverage:** The security requirements (SRQ1-SRQ14) demonstrated the value of the model-driven method for assessing the Mistral AI architecture.
 - Phase 1: The security coverage for this phase was low at 34.8%. This was not least expected, as the security control had not been applied to the model’s architecture. This confirms the initial hypothesis that gaps exist in the system without applied security requirements, as indicated by the scores assigned to this phase by the experts.
 - Phase 2: There is a 74.8% security requirements coverage in this phase, rising to more than double that of the previous phase, where the security requirements are not applied. This provides evidence that our method successfully elicits and specifies the necessary security requirements to address identified threats.

The results show that the experts’ scoring improved during the second phase of assessing the Mistral AI system, which incorporated applied security requirements. The increases in Exp1 from 20% to 92%, Exp2 from 61% to 80%, and Exp3 from 23.6% to 56.4% demonstrate that the proposed approach and security requirements were clear, relevant, and effectively addressed the security gaps (“Fully” or “partially fulfilled”) perceived in Phase 1.

3. **Trustworthiness Coverage:** A combination of both the functional and security coverage to determine the trustworthiness of the Mistral AI system. The low score of 49.6% in phase 1 reflects that, while functionally capable, the system is deemed untrustworthy due to its security deficiencies. In the second phase, we observe an increase in the score 74.8% guided by our model-driven approach, which addresses the security concerns raised in the first phase of assessment. This directly enhances the overall trustworthiness (with respect to security) of the Mistral AI use case. The gaps identified also indicate that some functional and security requirements were not fully addressed by the Mistral AI system, providing areas for future refinement of the model.

6.4.1 Resolve phase

During the assessment, the ML engineer raised questions regarding the security aspects of the presented instantiated model. Following an interdisciplinary discussion, it was concluded that, while the ML Engineer lacked expertise in security, their judgment remains valuable. Their perspective on their judgments would be based on the perception of the system’s trustworthiness, including reliability and robustness, as well as their understanding of the AI system’s architecture.

7 Conclusion

This report presents the foundation of the research on Model-driven elicitation of functional and security requirements of AI-supported systems. The work was established through a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) which synthesised the knowledge on AI assets, Lifecycle, Threats and Control measures. The conceptual model was developed from the results of the state-of-the-art analysis. The validation of the model was demonstrated through a feasibility study using

	Phase 1				Phase 2			
	Exp1	Exp2	Exp3		Exp1	Exp2	Exp3	
REQ1.1	2	2	5	9.0	1	4	5	10.0
REQ1.2	5	3	1	9.0	5	5	1	11.0
REQ1.3	5	3	1	9.0	4	4	1	9.0
REQ1.4	5	3	5	13.0	5	4	5	14.0
REQ2.1	5	2	4	11.0	5	4	4	13.0
REQ2.2	1	2	1	4.0	1	4	1	6.0
REQ2.3	5	4	5	14.0	5	4	5	14.0
REQ2.4	5	3	5	13.0	5	4	5	14.0
REQ3.1	3	3	3	9.0	3	5	3	11.0
REQ4.1	4	3	5	12.0	5	4	5	14.0
REQ4.2	5	4	1	10.0	2	4	1	7.0
	81.8%	58.2%	65.5%	68.5%	74.5%	83.6%	65.5%	74.5%
SRQ1	1	2	1	4.0	5	4	5	14.0
SRQ2	1	3	2	6.0	2	4	1	7.0
SRQ3	1	3	1	5.0	5	4	1	10.0
SRQ4	1	3	1	5.0	5	4	5	14.0
SRQ5	1	3	1	5.0	5	4	5	14.0
SRQ6	1	3	1	5.0	5	4	1	10.0
SRQ7	1	3	1	5.0	4	4	1	9.0
SRQ8	1	3	1	5.0	5	4	1	10.0
SRQ9	1	3	1	5.0	4	4	1	9.0
SRQ10	1	3	1	5.0	5	4	5	14.0
SRQ11	1	3	1	5.0	5	4	5	14.0
SRQ12	1	3	1	5.0	4	4	1	9.0
SRQ13	1	3	3	7.0	5	4	5	14.0
SRQ14	1	4	1	6.0	4	4	1	9.0
	20.0%	61.8%	23.6%	34.8%	92.7%	80.0%	56.4%	74.8%
Over all Trustworthiness coverage				49.6%				74.7%

Figure 10: Functionality, Security and Trustworthiness coverage of Mistral AI Model

the Z-Inspection process. By instantiating the Mistral AI Large Language Model Architecture and guiding assessments based on functional and security requirements, we demonstrated its effectiveness as a framework for evaluating the trustworthiness (with respect to security) of an AI-supported system. The results of the method's feasibility demonstrate that the application of security requirements derived from our proposed model led to a 25.1% increase in the overall perceived trustworthiness, with security coverage doubling from 34.8% to 74%. This qualitative validation confirms the proposed model's ability to stimulate discussions and highlights critical gaps in the security of AI-supported systems. In conclusion, this report provides a blueprint for the development of the conceptual model and offers an evaluation for the trustworthiness of AI-supported systems.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest in this report.

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Figure 13: Instantiation of security controls to the Mistral AI

Figure 14: Security requirements instantiation of the Mistral AI

Figure 15: instantiation of Functional Requirements for Baseline T5 System

Figure 16: instantiation of Functional Requirements for Llama-3.2 System

Figure 17: instantiation of Functional Requirements for Llama-3.3 System

Figure 18: instantiation of Functional Requirements for Qwen3 System

Figure 19: instantiation of Functional Requirements for Duplex System

Figure 20: instantiation of Functional Requirements for OpenELM System